

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

BASIC CONCEPTS ABOUT AUDIOVISUAL METHOD

Hasanova M.

Senior laborant of the chair "English and methods"

Nakhchivan State University, Azerbaijan

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Abstract

Audio-visual method combines vision and sound which are very effective in foreign language learning. Films, clips, TV show programs and newlines in English are of great significance in L2 acquisition. The usage of native language is ignored while teaching the foreign language through this method. Application of Audio-visual materials only lacks speaking skill. Since there is no one to build up a communication with. A learner can easily polish his/her reading, writing and listening skills. However, all these three skills help to develop speaking skill, as well. The Audio-visual method is composed of educational digital materials. For this reason, it is sometimes called educational material. Hence, "audio-visual aids" or teaching materials refer to such technologies which attempt to make knowledge understandable to us through our senses.

Keywords: television, audio-visual materials, media, DVD, Audio-visual method

Educational tools that can convey meaning without just depending on spoken symbols or language are frequently referred to as audiovisual materials [10].

Textbook or reference material is not included in the scope of audiovisual teaching aids. Shabiralani, Hasan, Hamad, and Iqbal note that primary school students learn more easily and quickly with audiovisual devices than with verbal instruction. Their study's findings also showed that the majority of educators and learners view the usage of visual aids favorably. Mercedes and Amelia, [9] highlights the effectiveness of visual material in learning, estimating that approximately 40% of what is acquired is achieved through visual experience, 25% through auditory, 17% through touch, 15% through various organization, and 3% through taste and smell. This claim clarifies the value of audiovisual assets in the teaching and learning process. The audiovisual method is one of the methods that can be used in the classroom during the lesson for kindergarten and primary school students. This method allows users to make effective use of both visual and audio media and also enables the inclusion of educational materials. Improvement of access to electronic and multimedia technologies and their accessibility have enabled more students to actively participate in the educational process. Teaching and learning are more successful and valuable when using audiovisual aids. This is one of the best ways to spread knowledge and information. The use of audiovisual means such as television, video, cinema, projector, computer in the lesson helps to enrich students' cognition, stimulates their interest, and creates a creative environment.

Audio visuals are an important part of education today as they help students learn better. This is one of the reasons why the use of audiovisuals in teaching, learning and research has increased over the years. The speed with which students can instantly access information and share it with others has increased dramatically. Moreover, students are already able to understand concepts and ideas better and faster. Thanks to

audiovisual media, there have been great advances in education in the last few decades.

In the era of teaching modern languages, various innovations are applied in the ELT industry that go beyond the traditional teaching approaches. The current trend is towards communicative language teaching rather than traditional grammar teaching. The urge to learn a new language has evolved into a communicative need; in the past, acquiring a new language meant learning to read literature in that language. To converse with members of other cultures who speak other languages, people study a second language in addition to their home tongue. As a result, language is taught as a tool for communication rather than as a topic. As a result, methodologies and learning strategies have been modified to meet the evolving demands of language learning. In an effort to improve the effectiveness of their instruction, foreign language teachers always seek for new innovations. It is not simple to teach a language, thus the material should be engaging enough to help students get past their anxieties.

Audiovisuals are learning devices used in the classroom to stimulate learning and make learning easier and more enjoyable. It follows Farouk's A.V.A. so-called audio-visual aids or teaching materials are aids that try to make knowledge clear to us through our senses [4, p. 56]. Meanwhile, according to Francis, the term *audiovisual materials* is usually used to refer to teaching materials that can be used to convey meaning without relying entirely on verbal symbols or language. In other words, A.V.As are teaching materials used by teachers to present the material in an attractive way to facilitate the auditory and visual experience of the student [5]. Authentic materials always facilitate the learning process. Babayev Javid underlines the importance of authentic materials: "They make the students face with real life situations. The students live the situations in real life and these materials willy-nilly depict native speakers' words and behaviours. They are not worse than the artificial texts given in created materials that

have been especially written to exhibit special grammatical rules or relation types.” [2, p.33].

According to the Terrebonne Parish Library System, Audio-visual convey information primarily through sound and images rather than through text. As students become more accustomed to technology, the role of audiovisual materials in the classroom is increasing. Students learn in different ways, so using audiovisual components helps improve the learning environment.

The audiovisual method is one of the methods that can be used in the lesson during the lesson for elementary school students. It uses both visual and audio media and allows you to embed learning materials. Improved access and accessibility of electronic and multimedia technologies have enabled more students to participate in classes. For this reason online lessons also provide the students audio-visual materials. Babayev Javid emphasizes the significance of online learning in his article: “it has become a reality for everyone to recognize and accept online learning as a priority” [3, p.67]

Audio-visual method is also called educational material. Sound literally means "hearing" and "sight" means revealed through sight. Thus, "audio-visual aids" or teaching materials refer to all such technologies that attempt to make knowledge understandable to us through our senses. All of these instructional tools give us first-hand knowledge through the senses of hearing and seeing while making the learning scenarios as realistic as feasible. Thus, audiovisual content can be seen as any tool that can be utilized to enhance the learning process by making it more dynamic, realistic, and concrete. Through our senses, we learn. Experiences give us knowledge. Every sense aids in our ability to perceive our surroundings. The majority of the information we learn in school is absorbed through our eyes and hearing. Reading is less significant than doing in our educational system. You can make theoretical, linguistic, and dull things more natural and enjoyable. Audio-visual materials According to Brinton, audio-visual materials are educational materials that present information to students that do not require the use of paper and pencil. Audiovisual materials are useful in teaching because they take the teaching away from a textbook-only approach. Computers, televisions, cassettes, video or DVD discs and projectors, radios are all types of audiovisual material. Posters, cartoons, clothes, models and tours are also audiovisual. In the classroom, films, audio recordings, and videotapes can be used as substitutes for face-to-face student-teacher communication. These forms of education can be used in continuous public schools where there are not enough teachers. Typically, informative and motivational films and videotapes on selected topics aired on various television networks are typical of this type of material, providing real-life depth for students. Here, teachers can use audiovisual materials to reinforce their teaching in a lecture or activity-based lesson context. After that, teachers can show any motivational film according to the requirements of the situation and the relevant topic.

Mere words written or spoken by a teacher cannot and will not provide an adequate learning experience.

We have to complete the teacher's words. In this regard, visual aids in the form of pictures, cards, posters, etc. help a lot. Again, listening in the language is a very important skill. If we do not have the opportunity to listen to a language, we will not be able to speak it properly. Thus, poetry, fairy tales, etc. audio cassettes containing statements are needed. Such materials will be not only interesting but also motivating for the student.

The use of audiovisuals in the educational environment is important in many ways. Part of their importance is that they can adapt to different learning styles, which ensures effective learning. Some mature learners learn best when they see what is being said. Additionally, others learn best when they can touch or experience something as it is taught to them. Others may fully understand by relying on hearing alone, etc. Aggarwal, Lumsdaine, and Glaser (1960) explain that the effectiveness of students in acquiring new knowledge, skills, and abilities depends on the methods used and the students' learning styles what techniques to use.

Televisions are still used in some classrooms today instead of projections. Some teachers still use tapes to show movies on TVs, but more and more people are using DVD players, one of the achievements of the digital revolution. Many classrooms don't even need a separate player because modern computers have DVD drives. Using a computer to play DVDs in the classroom requires a computer projector, but many classrooms are increasingly equipped with this latest audiovisual equipment. Audiovisual materials are now often in the form of a computer file played using software installed on the teacher's computer. Instead of purchasing DVDs for classroom use, schools sometimes subscribe to digital video services, such as United Streaming, which is available through Discovery Education. These services provide Internet access to tens of thousands of videos—far more than any teacher could have in their classroom collection. Access is immediate; no need to wait for the goods to be shipped.

Mamun investigated the use of AVA in teaching. The purpose of the study was to investigate the benefits of language teachers as well as students using audiovisual aids in teaching English. In addition, other experts found more extensive research on the use of A.V.A. Mathew and Alidmat reviewed the usefulness of AVA in an undergraduate EFL classroom, and as a result, AVA became one of the learning tools that helped most students [7]. Meanwhile, Merdas investigated students' active vocabulary more deeply [8]. The results show that A.V.A plays an extremely important role in increasing students' ability to use active vocabulary.

As you know, the teacher uses different approaches to teach his students, helping them to learn actively. Over the years, teachers' efforts in the field of education have included various methods and techniques. One such method used by teachers to ensure effective teaching is the use of audiovisual aids [1]. Audiovisual resources engage students and help teachers illustrate concepts easily. These audiovisual resources are mainly teaching aids used in the classroom to help and encourage students to understand the context. Au-

audiovisual media, in Burton's opinion, encourage and facilitate efficient learning. In addition, Kinder suggested that the learning process can be made more realistic, accurate and active by using audiovisual resources [6]. Typically, this type of learning is not fostered in most school systems. Implementing this learning in the classroom requires a lot of knowledge and experience.

Many teachers who use these audiovisual resources in their classrooms lack the experience required to get the most out of these tools. Rather, they use these resources to relieve students of the burden of explaining context. For example, some teachers use a text description, illustration or video presentation of the topics they want to teach and just start the presentation without explaining anything properly and thus the lecture time passes easily. Teachers should plan properly before using audiovisuals [11]. In addition, teachers are not working on their students' visual literacy.

The word CREDIF, which stands for the audiovisual approach, was initially used in France in the 1950s. At the beginning of learning a second or foreign language, this approach is meant to teach common language. It was founded on a behaviorist theory that claims language is learned via the development of habits. It is based on the assumption that foreign language is essentially a mechanical process and is more effective if the spoken form precedes the written language. Emphasis was placed on speaking skills and a carefully structured sequence of exercises, as well as the idea that the quality and consistency of learning is directly proportional to the amount of practice performed.

The principle of audiovisual method is as the followings:

- * Picker
- * Training
- * Physical control
- * Correct presentation
- * Answer

Teachers employ teaching tools, such as audiovisual aids, to help pupils understand specific ideas more clearly and successfully. These books can be used for a variety of English teaching objectives. The connection of the learning material to the subject being studied, the accomplishment of a learning objective, and its appropriate use are all indicators of its efficacy.

Good learning is the cornerstone of any educational program, as F. W. Noel clearly observes. This foundation includes visual teaching tools. As a result, an English teacher needs to be knowledgeable about the several audio-visual tools available to him.

The use of audiovisual elements to stimulate and facilitate the acquisition of a second language is well established.

Language learners can benefit from a variety of media and visual presentation approaches, according to Wright [13, p. 1]. In other words, if used properly and at the appropriate times, all audiovisual products benefit language learning. The learner employs both his eyes and hearing when learning and teaching a language, but his eyes are the key to learning.

Research shows that most students in a regular classroom need to see information visually to remember it. Visual learning encourages students to process

what they see and filter it in their brains because they see that ideas are connected, organized, and connected. Visual learning has expanded teaching methods in schools by providing students with simpler methods so that any subject they learn can be fully explained visually. New concepts are easier to understand, especially if they can be related to the previous topic.

River says that it amplifies the benefits of learning another culture by putting listeners and viewers in indirect contact with native speakers [12, p.399].

There are some characteristics that can be used to determine how important audiovisuals are in the learning process. And their value depends on how well they help to achieve the goals of the guidelines and can be summarized under the following headings:

- Compatibility
- Accuracy
- Interest
- Clarity
- Motivation
- Realism

When choosing and using visual aids, we should try to select as aids that connect new experiences with past experiences and that are already in the minds of the students who will use them.

A visual medium must have the quality and niche to develop real ideas about different areas of life. Instead, we can try to develop in our students a concept very similar to the idea of the movement of electrons in an atom. In this case, we teachers try to describe it as accurately as possible with the help of diagrams and tables, and students are shown a real film about the movement of electrons; a completely different but effective concept will emerge. Almost all visual aids lack some features, but the actual example clarifies the concept through realism, so that learners experience this fact in a hands-on approach to learning and understanding.

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